

Disability Activism: Emancipatory Discourse for Women

Jaswinder Kaur

Research Scholar, MCM DAV College for Women, Chandigarh

Corresponding author- **Jaswinder Kaur**

Email- Jaswinderk887887@gmail.com

Capitol Crawl²- A historical moment in the history of America whence persons with disabilities climbed the Capitol's steps after ditching their assisted devices to get the ADA, American Disability Act, 1990 passed. Considered the largest bill ever passed anywhere in the world for the rights of persons with disabilities. This bill actually remains the model source for disability legislation around the world even now. But the activism for the rights of the disabled started a decade before the ADA passed. For instance, disability rights organisations such as ADAPT fighting for justice for the accessibility of wheelchair users on public transportation for 35 years and many more are voicing the accessibility of the disabled into mainstream society.

Disability Activism took a turn when writers came into writing about their journeys through disability in the forms of biography, autobiography, memoirs and certain other genres. Contemporary writers are reclaiming it by writing under speculative fiction, young adult fiction and fantasy fiction. In writing, disability activism had a different path, the first generation of writers was chiefly male and rejected a curative approach to disability but the second generation of authors was females, some of them mothers to disabled children and was able to incorporate themes like gender discrimination and racial discrimination into ableism. (Ruthie Bonan, pp-3)

United Nations adopted a convention on the rights of persons with disabilities on 13 December 2006. United Nations CPRD explained "Discrimination on the basis of disability" means any distinction, exclusion or restriction on the basis of disability which has the purpose or effect of impairing or nullifying the recognition, enjoyment or exercise, on an equal basis with others, of all human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, civil or any other field. It includes all forms of discrimination," (General assembly, United Nations)

Photo: Jeff Markowitz/AP

Before moving further, it is important to know how the present understanding of ableism and disability studies came into existence. Different models of disability came into acceptance throughout the past by evolution in itself. The first model of disability was the charity model based on principles of religion in which the disabled are seen as people who are sinned or punished by God. One can have myriad examples of this model in any mythology. Say Indian or Greek. Characters like Manthara, Kubja, Ashtavakra, and many others caught disability out of some action in past but the cure to their problem is either prayers or alms.

The second model is the medical model which came into existence in the 19th century with the advancement in science and technology. It discarded the earlier model based on religion. Charles Darwin and his cousin brother Sir Francis Galton who promoted the idea of eugenics, (the idea of breeding better human beings) played significant roles in it. Medical model prescribed remedy/treatment to disabled. But then comes the social model of disability explaining disability as, not the product of sin, genetic disorder, trauma or other causes but the cultural, political and social practices in society that create disability. This is actually a diachronic study of models of disability. (Lennard Davis) It was the

first time in history with the acceptance of the social model of disability that the words 'impairment' and 'disability' were understood distinctively, 'impairment' as physical or mental limitation/inability but 'disability' as an effect of discrimination and lack of accommodation against people with impairments. Hence, the social model becomes the foundational model of disability studies.

The Disability theory gets its depth through disability analysis in theory and praxis as well. Representation of disability in cultural narratives is similar to femaleness, the way both are considered as "defective departures" (Rosemarie) from normalcy standards. Multiple examples can be viewed in history, the most popular ones are Saartjie Baartman, known as Hottentot Venus exhibiting racial and gendered degradation. She was not disabled, rather she was seen through a frame of abnormality, and the disability discourse represented her to the Western eye. The discourse of disability, gender, race, and environment (ecology) intertwine further in representing quashed people as invalid or inadequate. Marge Piercy in her poem *Unclearing not to Speak* writes pronouns like 'womb-man', 'toy', and 'penis-poor', in terms of castration presenting her as disabled. Yet the interconnection between Disability Studies and Ecofeminism seems far but certain points pave the way for further exploration for example toxicity production, both Ecofeminism and Disability Studies take into consideration the role of the environment in the discourse of body and its definition, especially in the area like toxicity in water deforestation, frailty caused by war and the newer concept like imperial colonialism.

Rosemarie Garland Thomson in her book *Extraordinary Bodies* extrapolated many existing parallels between the social meanings attributed to female bodies and those to disabled bodies. Both the female as well as the disabled are counted as inferior and deviant. The political subordination of women and the disabled to men (patriarchy) in home and in society. Aristotle gave the 'mutilated male' to the female. Freud also set out this idea of female subordination by linking it to castration. Moreover, contemporary feminists consider women as deformed and mutilated for example Jane Flax in her book *Thinking Fragments: Psychoanalysis, Feminism, and Postmodernism in the Contemporary West* says:

In male-dominated cultures, no woman escapes the consequences of such a position. Even the most independent woman is still mutilated and deformed by the ideas and social relations that more

deeply affect her less fortunate sisters. (137). Jasbir K Puar's book *Right to Maim: Debility, Capacity and Disability* pose a difficult but necessary question for the future of disability while explaining the issue of the Israel-Palestine conflict, as war is the biggest producer of disability. It explained how Israel occupied Palestine through Pronatalism, settler colonialism and also promoting state-sponsored terrorism but adopting "pinkwashing" along the way. The term "pinkwashing" is used to define the aggrandizement of Gay-friendliness by the state of Israel to deemphasise the occupation and mass murder of the population of Palestine. Patricia Berne, one of the founders of Sins Invalid, a disability justice performance group of artists with disabilities and gender variants artists wrote against the global effort to "pinkwash" Israel's image whence the group protested and agitated by withdrawing their documentary to be shown at Vancouver Queen's Film Festival in 2014 as the host accepted advertising funds from an organization known from "pinkwashing" during a time when Palestinians were killed by military bombarding of Gaza strip. At the end of the chapter, Puar explains the health politics, where Palestinians are twice disabled- through body injury and undercut or denied access to healthcare.

Rob Nixon's concept of "slow violence" of war is ground-breaking to explain environmental toxins and nuclear wastes which continue to degrade human health and environmental health for a number of years. Moreover, deprivation of healthy food and green surroundings. Unhealthy practices of living under hazards and toxins prove slow poison to people of color and poor individuals. Nixon sees its debility caused by war due to dilapidated healthcare systems and community capital due to Western military actions in the Third World. Crip theory began as an academic theory that too intersects with experiences like race, gender and sexuality with disability. Robert McRuer gave the term 'crip theory' which propounded major pillars in disability studies. Robert believes that compulsory able-bodiedness produces disability and that compulsory able-bodiedness is the agent of capitalism. Cultural systems as well as economics are driven by market priorities. From this angle, we can extend the scope of ecofeminism to include an examination of ableism and compulsory able-bodiedness. All the areas I opted for: disability studies, ecofeminism and fantasy fiction are vastly different with different agendas and emerged at different periods but even then, their interconnectivity can't be denied because all three include women, body and non-human

nature that surround them. Recent trends in neo-colonialism also emanated disability. Free trade agreements allow capital to flow freely across international borders by keeping in claw the dictates of the International Monetary Fund and World Bank. An unsustainable debt crisis to weaken nations economically, a continued shortage of food, horrid living conditions, and inadequate access to healthcare services have augmented the disability. A recent tragedy in the year 2012, the burning of Tazreen Fashion factory in the Ashulia district on the outskirts of Dhaka, Bangladesh where official figures claimed 124 casualties, very little attention was paid to women survivors of the accident. Many were amputated and suffered from severe burns and post-traumatic stress. The garments produced were meant to be exported to nations like the USA, Italy, Germany and the Netherlands. One of the buyers was the United States Marines, the maritime land force service branch of the United States Armed Forces. Many examples can be sought like this. What else has not been done by the US military deployed in Afghanistan, hundred thousand women suffered, many of them lost their lives many others were disabled.

When a country is invaded poor crips are considered a dispensable population, easy to be able to do the damage that occurs to land and to the disabled bodyminds (Margaret Price), to those marginalized people as they are typically viewed as sub-humans. (Louisiana Cancer Alley. Women Activist. To be added.)

The Flint water tank crisis started in 2014 is a textbook case of environmental racism where the groundwater was contaminated with high levels of lead and coagulation of specific types of diseases causing bacteria. A hundred thousand residents were exposed to certain ailments resulting reduction in intellectual functioning and IQ (mental disability), and an increased chance of Alzheimer's disease. It happened all because the state wanted to save a buck neglecting the rights of poor people. Dr Robert Bullard, a leading environmental justice advocate noted the race-based oppression in it. He says, "Racism trumps class even middle-income African American are more likely to live in more polluted neighbourhoods." Midnight Mine case is another addition to it. Twala Abrahamsen, a tribal woman working to get rid of water contamination. Her fight is twofold- against dangerous cancer-causing pollution and a larger issue of environmental racism. Environmental activist, Isabel Carrera Zamanillo from the University of Washington, College of

Environment as a Diversity, Equity and Inclusion program officer fighting against the damage caused.

Works Cited:

1. Bubar, Joe. *The Fight for the Disability Rights*, Junior Scholastic.
2. <https://junior.scholastic.com/pages/promotion/031521/the-fight-for-disability-rights.html?language=english#900L> [Accessed, Oct 2022] Davis, Lennard J., editor. *The Disability Studies Reader*. 5th ed., Routledge, 2016. Flax, Jane. *Thinking Fragments: Psychoanalysis, Feminism, and Postmodernism in the Contemporary West*. Berkeley: University of California Press, c1990 1990. <http://ark.cdlib.org/ark:/13030/ft6w1007qv/> Gomes, Ruthie Bonan, et al. "New Dialogues in Feminist Disability Studies." *Estudos Feministas*, vol. 27, no. 1, 2019, pp. 1–13. JSTOR, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26634954>. Accessed 20 Mar. 2022
3. Varkkey, Helena. "By exporting trash, rich countries put their waste out of sight and out of mind" CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/2019/07/29/opinions/by-exporting-trash-rich-countries-put-their-waste-out-of-sight-and-out-of-mind-varkey/index.html> Puar, Jasbir K. *The Right to Maim: Debility, Capacity, Disability*. Duke University Press, 2017. JSTOR, <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv11314kc>. Accessed 2 Feb. 2023
4. National Library of Science. *Environmental Neuroscience: Advancing the Understanding of How Chemical Exposures Impact Brain Health and Disease: Proceedings of a Workshop* <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK566974/#:~:text=These%20include220flame-retardant%20compounds,metals%2C%20pesticides%2C%20and%20herbicides.>
5. Natural Toxins in Food, World Health Organisation <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/natural-toxins-in-food>
6. "No Failure: Climate Change, Radical Hope, and Queer Crip Feminist Eco-Future", *Radical Philosophy Review*, 17(1): 203–225. <https://doi:10.5840/radphilrev201432614>
7. <https://www.npr.org/2020/12/21/946292119/oregon-hospitals-didnt-have-shortages-so-why-were-disabled-people-denied-care>
8. 2014, "No Failure: Climate Change, Radical Hope, and Queer Crip Feminist Eco-Future", *Radical Philosophy Review*, 17(1): 203–225. doi:10.5840/radphilrev201432614

9. Goodley, Dan, Kirsty Liddiard, and Katherine Runswick-Cole, 2018, "Feeling Disability: Theories of Affect and Critical Disability Studies", *Disability & Society*, 33(2): 197–217. doi:10.1080/09687599.2017.1402752
10. Dan, Kirsty Liddiard, and Katherine Runswick-Cole, 2018, "Feeling Disability: Theories of Affect and Critical Disability Studies", *Disability & Society*, 33(2): 197–217. <https://doi:10.1080/09687599.2017.1402752>
11. Dhaka garment factory fire. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2012_Dhaka_garment_factory_fire
12. United Nations. Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/convention-rights-persons-disabilities>